

IoT System Testing Taxonomy

We are currently doing research on IoT systems testing. We developed a taxonomy to guide IoT system testers by availing all aspects to be considered. We included all possible types of testing to help testers systematically and comprehensively. We are looking for industry practitioners to provide their feedback in terms of completeness, understandability, and usability. This research has received ethical certificate from Canada Research Chairs Secretariat.

About the Participants and Their Prior Knowledge

1. Where do you work? [company and address]

2. What is your experience in IoT?

Une seule réponse possible.

- Less than 1 Year
- Between 1 and 3 Years
- Between 3 and 5 Years
- Between 5 and 10 Years
- More than 10 Years

3. Choose your expertise among the following IoT components?

Plusieurs réponses possibles.

- Device Layer (also known as sensing layer or physical layer)
- Network Layer (also known as transport layer or gateway layer)
- Cloud Layer (sometimes known as service layer)
- Application Layer
- Business Layer
- Edge Layer
- Fog Layer
- User Layer

4. Which of the following IoT application domains are you in?

Plusieurs réponses possibles.

- Smart Cities (Smart Parking, Smart Roads, Smart Lightings, Structural Health Monitoring, Surveillance, Emergency Response, etc.)
- Home Automation (Smart Lighting, Smart Appliances, Intrusion Detection, Smoke/ Gaz Detectors, etc.)
- Health & Lifestyle (Health & Fitness Monitoring, Greenhouse Control, etc..)
- Environment (Water Monitoring, Air Pollution Monitoring, Noise Pollution Monitoring, Forest Fire Detection, Flood Detection, etc.)
- Agriculture (Smart Irrigation, Greenhouse Control, etc.)
- Retail (Smart payment, Smart Vending Machines, Inventory Management)
- Industry Automation (Machine Diagnosis & Prognosis, Indoor Air Quality Monitoring, etc.)
- Logistics (Fleet Tracking, Shipment Monitoring, Remote Vehicle Diagnostics,etc.)
- Energy (Smart Grids, Renewable Energy Systems, Prognostics,etc.).
- Others

5. In your company, who do the testing for IoT systems?

Plusieurs réponses possibles.

- Testing Engineer
- Quality Assurance Engineer
- Developer
- Project Manager
- Business Analyst
- Service is outsourced
- None
- Others

6. Do you know any other taxonomy for IoT system testing?

Une seule réponse possible.

- Yes
- No

7. If you answered yes, can you share more details and possibly a copy or a link to that taxonomy.

Taxonomy Feedback

8. Is the proposed taxonomy understandable?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Excellent

9. Please explain your previous answer

10. Is the proposed taxonomy complete?

At what level the proposed taxonomy is complete? Does it cover all relevant concepts related to IoT systems testing?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Very exhaustive

11. Please explain your choice for previous answer

12. How useful for the IoT system testers is the proposed taxonomy?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Very useful

13. Please explain your choice on previous answer

14. Does the proposed taxonomy help testers test their IoT systems?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Very Helpful

15. Please explain your choice on previous answer

16. Is the level of details of the proposed taxonomy appropriate?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Very Very appropriate

17. Please explain your choice on previous answer

18. How accurately does the proposed taxonomy cover the concepts of IoT system testing?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely accurate

19. Please explain your choice on previous answer

20. Do the main categories of the proposed taxonomy match your expectations?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely well

21. Please explain your choice on previous answer

22. Does this taxonomy help you to better prepare test strategy?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Extremely well

23. Please explain your choice on previous answer

24. Overall, how do you rate the importance of this taxonomy for IoT system practitioners?

Une seule réponse possible.

0 1 2 3 4 5

Not Very important to the practitioners

25. Please explain your previous answer in more details

Open Questions for Participants and Follow-up

26. Do the main categories of the proposed taxonomy miss any important aspects of IoT system testing?

27. Would you like to receive the final version of this taxonomy? If yes, please provide your e-mail address below.

28. Would you agree to be interviewed about this taxonomy? If yes, please provide your e-mail address below.

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